

How many species of *Candidula* (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) in northern Portugal?

¿Cuántas especies de *Candidula* (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) habitan en el norte de Portugal?

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ABSTRACT

Two species of *Candidula* Kobelt, 1871 (Pulmonata: Hygromiidae) endemic to Portugal are reported from the northern part of the country. *C. belemensis* (Servain, 1880) is considered a valid species similar to, but different from the widespread *C. intersecta* (Poiret, 1801). *C. olisippensis* (Servain, 1880) is distinctive, having a shell with very small, round umbilicus, a long spermathecal duct, and a short flagellum.

RESUMEN

Se citan para el norte de Portugal dos especies endémicas en este país pertenecientes al género *Candidula* Kobelt, 1871 (Pulmonata: Hygromiidae). *C. belemensis* (Servain, 1880) es considerada como una especie válida similar, pero diferente, a la ampliamente distribuida *C. intersecta* (Poiret, 1801). *C. olisippensis* (Servain, 1880) es de fácil distinción, al tener una concha con un ombligo redondeado y pequeño, un largo conducto de la espermateca y un corto flagelo.

KEY WORDS: Gastropoda, Hygromiidae, *Candidula*, Portugal, distribution, taxonomy.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Gastropoda, Hygromiidae, *Candidula*, Portugal, distribución, taxonomía.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Candidula* Kobelt, 1871 comprises several species of hygromiid land snails living in Western Europe. In the Iberian Peninsula this genus has undergone a remarkable diversification, particularly along the Atlantic drainages (ALTONAGA, GÓMEZ, MARTÍN, PRIETO, PUENTE AND RALLO, 1994). The taxonomy of this genus is complex because the diagnostic characters of the various species are not conspicuous, either in

the internal anatomy or in the shells. The species of *Candidula* living in Portugal are still poorly known, yet this country has at least four endemics (ALTIMIRA, 1969; GITTENBERGER, 1985, 1993). This note is a contribution towards a revision of the genus in the Iberian Peninsula (Ondina and Altaba, *in prep.*).

Two little-known, apparently rare species of *Candidula* are reported here, collected during a field trip in April

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1994 in northern Portugal. These species were described by SERVAIN (1880), and subsequently ignored for over a century (NOBRE, 1930, 1941; SEIXAS, 1992). Con-

chological and anatomical data indicate that the species studied here are indeed distinct taxa. The specimens are kept in the author's malacological collection.

RESULTS

Family HYGROMIIDAE Tryon, 1866

Genus *Candidula* Kobelt, 1871

Candidula belemensis (Servain, 1880) (Figs. 1, 2)

C. belemensis was known up to date only from the original locality (Lisbon) and three other sites further south (GITTENBERGER, 1993). A single fresh shell was found at the base of the old city walls of Valença do Minho, at the northern border of Portugal (UTM 29T NG25; Figs. 1, 2). This locality represents a considerable extension of the species' known range. It is likely, however, that *C. belemensis* lives also further north, in Galicia, where specimens having a long flagellum have been reported as *C. intersepta* by CASTILLEJO (1986).

This species is probably closely related to *C. intersepta* (Poiret, 1801), which ranges discontinuously throughout Atlantic Europe, from southern Portugal to southern Sweden (KERNEY AND CA-

MERON, 1979; GITTENBERGER, 1993; ALTONAGA *et al.*, 1994). *C. belemensis* differs conchologically from the latter in having a more depressed shell with a broader aperture, a wide and slightly eccentric umbilicus, and a much shallower sculpture of radial ribs and minute spiral striae (GITTENBERGER, 1993).

Anatomically it differs from NW-European *C. intersepta* in the relatively longer flagellum, which is about half the length of the epiphallus (GITTENBERGER, 1993). However, populations of *C. intersepta* from NW-Iberia have a flagellum shorter than half the length of the epiphallus, as is typical of that species (MANGA GONZÁLEZ, 1979). Thus, the available evidence suggests that *C. belemensis* is not conspecific with co-occurring *C. intersepta*.

Candidula olisippensis (Servain, 1880) (Figs. 3-6)

Two subadult specimens were collected under boulders in the vicinity of the Sanctuary of Sameiro, near Braga (UTM 29T NF59; Figs. 3, 4). Although the aperture edge of their shells was still tender and became damaged, it bears a conspicuous whitish internal rib. The radulae have one central, and 22 and 24 lateral teeth. These numbers fall within the range of other *Candidula* species from northwestern Iberia (MANGA GONZÁLEZ, 1979).

The genitalia (still immature) of both specimens are shown in Figures 5 and 6. The flagellum is distinct, proximally narrow, and very short, measuring about $\frac{1}{4}$ the length of the epiphallus, which is somewhat shorter and thinner than the

penis. The bursa is small, oblong and indistinctly united to its duct, which lies appressed to the spermoviduct throughout and is exceedingly long, measuring almost twice the length of the penis and epiphallus combined. There are no glandulae mucosae, their location being occupied instead by a moderate swelling at the proximal end of the vagina. The dart sac appears partially developed, being only a large medial swelling of the vagina with no trace of a dart, but exhibiting two large internal longitudinal folds adjacent to two shallow invaginations, the lower one bordered by a few papillae. This internal structure can be interpreted as an immature stage of that described for other species of *Candidula*

Figures 1-4. Shells of *Candidula* from northern Portugal. 1, 2: *C. belemensis* from Valença do Minho (CRA 4895); 3, 4: *C. olisippensis* from Sameiro, near Braga (CRA 4866-1). Scale bar 5 mm.
 Figuras 1-4. Conchas de *Candidula* del norte de Portugal. 1, 2: *C. belemensis* de Valença do Minho (CRA 4895); 3, 4: *C. olisippensis* de Sameiro, cerca de Braga (CRA 4866-1). Escala 5 mm.

Figures 5, 6. Proximal genitalia of two immature specimens of *Candidula olisippensis*.
 Abbreviations. A: atrium; E: epiphallus; F: flagellum; M: penial retractor muscle; P: penis; S: bursa copulatrix; SD: duct of the bursa; SO: spermoviduct; V: vagina; VD: vas deferens. Scale bar 2 mm.
 Figuras 5, 6. Genitalia proximal de dos especimenes imaduros de *Candidula olisippensis*.
 Abreviaturas. A: atrio; E: epifalo; F: flagelo; M: músculo retractor penial; P: pene; S: bursa copulatrix; SD: conducto de la bursa; SO: espermoviducto; V: vagina; VD: vaso deferente. Escala 2 mm.

(HAUSDORF, 1988, 1991), confirming the generic assignation by GITTEBERGER (1993), who examined a dried specimen in poor condition.

Several nominal species described by LOCARD (1899) are probably synonyms of *Helix olisippensis* Servain 1880. The general shape of the shell in this species (or species complex) is fairly variable, yet it is always fairly thin, with

rounded or slightly angular periphery, very narrow roundish umbilicus, spire formed by flattened whorls separated by an indented suture, radial sculpture moderately developed, and microspiral striae well marked (GITTEBERGER, 1993). *Candidula olisippensis* is apparently endemic to Portugal. The current finding represents the northern limit of its known range.

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